

PHYSIOLOGY AND REPRODUCTION

Successful chilling of red-legged partridge (*Alectoris rufa*) sperm for use in artificial insemination

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ABSTRACT The fertilizing capacity of pure, fresh avian semen may disappear in just half an hour, hindering its successful use in artificial insemination (AI) projects. Longer storage requires the use of infra-physiological temperatures and of semen diluents that help preserve the spermatozoa but that do not interfere with their fertilizing capacity. This study examines the effect on sperm quality of storing red-legged partridge sperm for 3 h at 5°C with 2 different semen extenders: 1) a medium referred to as L&R-84, composed of sodium glutamate, glucose, magnesium acetate, potassium acetate, and polyvinylpyrrolidone, and 2) Lake 7.1 medium, composed of sodium glutamate, glucose, magnesium acetate, potassium citrate, and N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl)taurine (BES). Extending

with L&R-84 returned better curvilinear velocity ($P < 0.01$), straight-line velocity ($P < 0.01$), average path velocity ($P < 0.01$), linearity ($P < 0.05$), straightness ($P < 0.05$), and wobble ($P < 0.05$) values, while extending with the Lake 7.1 medium was associated with higher percentages ($P < 0.001$) of motile sperm. The fertility rate was higher ($P < 0.05$) when birds were inseminated with L&R-84-extended sperm than with Lake 7.1-extended sperm. The mean number of penetrations of perivitelline layer samples (taken from above the germinal disc) was also higher for the L&R-84-extended sperm ($P < 0.05$). These results show L&R-84 can be recommended as an extender for red-legged partridge semen to be stored for at least 3 h at 5°C.

Key words: artificial insemination, semen preservation, semen diluent, red-legged partridge, fertility

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INTRODUCTION

The breeding population of red-legged partridges (*Alectoris rufa*), which is confined to Europe, is estimated to be decreasing (IUCN, 2017). The wild populations of red-legged partridges in the Iberian Peninsula have declined sharply since the 1970 s, and it has been accompanied by an increase in game-farm facilities producing birds for release with the aim of maintaining hunting quotas (Casas and Viñuela, 2010; Díaz-Fernández et al., 2012). In addition, genetic introgression from chukar partridges (*Alectoris chukar*), is threatening the genetic integrity of wild Spanish

birds (Tejedor et al., 2007; Blanco-Aguilar et al., 2008; Casas et al., 2013). *Alectoris rufa* x *Alectoris chukar* hybrids have been long preferred by breeders, since they are less stress sensitive under captive conditions (Campo et al., 2015) and have a longer laying period and heavier body weight (Potts, 1989). However, artificial selection under farm conditions has led these hybrid birds to commonly show reduced anti-predator behavior and reduced broodiness. Artificial insemination (AI) may be of use in breeding programs aimed at the conservation of pure red-legged partridges by allowing the selection of desirable traits—including the maintenance of an appropriate anti-predator response and normal broodiness.

Unfortunately, the fertilizing capacity of fresh, pure avian semen can be lost in just half an hour, hindering its successful use in AI (reviewed by Blesbois and Brillard, 2007). Longer storage requires the use of infra-physiological temperatures to reduce sperm metabolism and achieve a reversible quiescent-like state, which helps prevent accelerated senescence. Extenders are

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required that assist in the preservation of sperm cells under such conditions but that do not reduce their fertilizing capacity. The literature contains no information on the use of extenders to prolong the time that partridge semen can be stored when chilled. AI has been successfully used in red-legged partridges, but always with fresh, undiluted semen used immediately after its collection (Abouelezz et al., 2015a).

The initial choice of extender for use with the semen of wild species is usually based on data obtained in related domestic species (Ciereszko et al., 2011; Seigneurin et al., 2013; Bushra et al., 2016), but it must eventually be tuned to the target species for use in *in vitro* and *in vivo* protocols (Leibo and Songsasen, 2002). For partridges, which are galliforms, the chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) is a useful model: not only is it a related species—and most types of galliform sperm have similar morphological characteristics (Santiago-Moreno et al., 2016)—but the cryopreservation of its sperm has been amply studied (Blesbois and Brillard 2007; Blesbois et al., 2007). However, interspecific variation in sperm cell membrane biochemical composition and fluidity finally determine whether an extender successful in one species will be so in another (Blesbois, 2012).

Lake extenders are widely employed in both chilling (Wilcox 1960; Bajpai and Brown, 1963; Lake and Ravie, 1979), and freezing (Lake and Stewart 1978; Lake and Ravie, 1984; Seigneurin and Blesbois 1995) rooster sperm. Given the drop in pH experienced by this species' semen when stored at 5°C (Lake and Ravie, 1979), the addition of strong buffers (e.g., zwitterion buffers) is recommended (Villaverde-Morcillo et al., 2016). The type of buffering additives used and the interactions of these with other ingredients in the extender (which may be species dependent) can affect sperm viability. Other commonly used extender components, such as glycerol, may alter the functionality of the avian genital tract by changing its osmolality, the properties of the luminal fluid, or the motion pattern of cilia (Hammerstedt and Graham, 1992). Egg yolk, especially at high concentrations (Abouelezz et al., 2015b), markedly reduces the fertilizing capacity of chilled rooster (Wilcox, 1960) and turkey (Bajpai and Brown, 1963) sperm by directly affecting sperm cell respiration (Fewlass et al., 1975). The incorporation of antibiotics (Bajpai and Brown, 1963) and the extender's final osmolality (Blanco et al., 2000) also may affect sperm viability.

This study compares the effects of chilled storage on red-legged partridge sperm diluted with Lake extenders—one containing an external cryoprotectant, the other a zwitterion buffer—as measured by sperm quality and post-AI fertility tests.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals

The semen donor birds were 32 adult red-legged partridge males (2 to 3 yr of age) housed (in groups of 2

to 3 birds) in outdoor cages (90 cm long x 82 cm wide x 60 cm high) under natural photoperiod (from 10 h 17' to 16 h 3' light/day [winter to summer solstices], including twilight) and temperature conditions at the El Encín Research Station (Alcalá de Henares, Spain [40° 31' N]). The average monthly temperature of the area ranges from 4°C to 24°C. The Research Station is placed in a warm and temperate region. There is more rainfall in the winter than in the summer. The average annual rainfall of this region is about 425 mm. Forty-four adult female birds (2 to 3 yr of age), housed in individual outdoor cages (111 cm long x 41 cm wide x 100 cm high) under the same conditions as above, were used in the AI experiments. The birds were maintained in a variable number during 2 consecutive yr (2015/2016), according the experimental design. The first yr, 19 adult red-legged partridge males were used as semen donor birds for the studies about motility variables; 16 of them also were used to assay seminal plasma osmolality. In the second yr, the same 19 males and 13 additional donor birds were used for AI procedures. Each yr, 22 different females were inseminated.

All birds were fed (*ad libitum*) a commercial feed containing 16% CP, 2700 kcal of ME/kg, 3.5% Ca, and 0.5% available P. Periodically, they were supplemented with amino acids and vitamins (Promotor L[®], Laboratorios Calier S.A, Barcelona, Spain) via their water.

All animals were handled according to procedures approved by the INIA Ethics Committee, and experiments were performed in accordance with the Spanish Policy for Animal Protection (RD53/2013), which conforms to European Union Directive 86/609 regarding the protection of animals used in scientific experiments.

Sperm Collection, Assessment of Sperm Variables, and Seminal Plasma Osmolality

Semen was collected during the breeding season (March to July) using the massage technique of Burrows and Quinn (1937), as adapted to this species (Santiago-Moreno et al., 2015). Two people were required for sperm collection. One caught a male and held him firmly over a table—one hand holding the legs and the other immobilizing the body and wings. The other person stimulated the bird, simultaneously stroking the back with the right hand and the abdomen with the left hand. The male birds were then “milked” by making the copulatory organ protrude by mild stimulation and then gripping its base with the thumb and index finger of the right hand. Semen was recovered by capillarity using a microhaematocrit tube (Brand[®] GMBH + Co KG, Wertheim, Germany). Samples for sperm analysis were immediately diluted 1:1 (v:v) at ambient temperature using one of 2 Lake media, according to the experimental design (see below). Diluted semen was immediately refrigerated at 5°C for 3 h before use (see below).

The osmolality of the seminal plasma was studied to provide a physiological reference value to be taken into account when diluting sperm samples with the

experimental extenders (see Experimental Design). Osmolality was measured in the seminal plasma of 14 pooled samples of non-diluted, fresh semen collected from 16 randomly chosen birds. The plasma was separated immediately after sperm collection by centrifugation at 600 *g* for 10 minutes. Measurements were made using a Model 3300 Advanced™ Micro Osmometer (Advance Instruments INC, Norwood, MA).

Sperm volume was calculated by measuring the length of the semen column in the microcapillary tube using a plastic ruler (accuracy ± 1 mm) and calculating the equivalent in volume units (μL).

Sperm concentration and motility were assayed as previously described (Santiago-Moreno et al., 2012) using a computer-aided sperm analyses (**CASA**) system coupled to a phase contrast microscope (Nikon Eclipse model 50i; Nikon Instruments Europe B.V., Izasa S.A.; negative contrast) and employing Sperm Class Analyzer (SCA[®], Barcelona, Spain) v.4.0. software (Microptic S.L., Barcelona, Spain). For motility analysis, sperm samples were diluted to a concentration of approximately 40 million sperm/mL and loaded onto warmed (38°C) 20 μm Leja[®] 8-chamber slides (Leja Products B.V., Nieuw-Vennep, The Netherlands). The percentage of motile spermatozoa and the percentage showing progressive motility (spermatozoa swimming forward quickly in a straight line) were recorded. Sperm movement characteristics—curvilinear velocity (**VCL**), straight-line velocity (**VSL**), average path velocity (**VAP**), amplitude of lateral head displacement (**ALH**), and beat-cross frequency (**BCF**)—also were recorded. Three progression ratios, expressed as percentages, were calculated from the velocity measurements described above: linearity ($\text{LIN} = \text{VSL}/\text{VCL} \times 100$), straightness ($\text{STR} = \text{VSL}/\text{VAP} \times 100$), and wobble ($\text{WOB} = \text{VAP}/\text{VCL} \times 100$). A minimum of 3 fields and 500 sperm tracks was evaluated at a magnification of 100x for each sample (image acquisition rate 25 frames/s).

Egg Penetration Assay

The eggs used in this assay, collected over 4 wk post AI, were stored at 15°C until analysis within 7 d of collection, as recommended by Bramwell et al. (1996). Directly above the germinal disc, a portion (around 1 cm^2) of the ovum perivitelline layer was removed, rinsed, straightened on a microscope slide, fixed with 20% formalin, and stained with Schiff's fuchsin-suphite reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). The number of holes made by sperms in the stained portion of the perivitelline membrane was counted by magnification $\times 100$ under a light microscope (Bramwell et al. 1995; Bramwell and Howarth 1997).

Artificial Insemination

All AI procedures involved the use of 30 μL diluted semen (15 μL semen plus 15 μL extender) and about 26×10^6 sperm cells/female partridge/insemination.

Prior to the AI procedure, the diluted semen was maintained chilled at 5°C about for 3 h in the presence of either L&R-84 or Lake 7.1 extender (see Experimental Design). AI was performed between 12:00 and 14:00 h using pooled semen samples from 32 males. Insemination involved gently everting the vaginal orifice of the females by applying a little pressure to the abdomen. The tip of a micropipette containing diluted semen was then gently inserted as far as possible (about 1.0 cm). Sperm was delivered while the pressure on the bird's abdomen was released, allowing the vaginal orifice to return to its normal position (Abouelezz et al. (2015a). Each female bird received 2 inseminations, 3 d apart.

All eggs laid by the inseminated birds were collected (daily) over the following 4 wk, starting from the second d after the first AI procedure. A total of 309 eggs was laid by inseminated birds over the experimental period (yr 2015 and 2016): 145 eggs were randomly collected for use in the egg penetration assay, and 164 eggs were incubated. Seventy-nine eggs from the L&R-84-sperm females, and 66 from the Lake 7.1-sperm females were randomly collected for use in the egg penetration assay (see above). The fertility rate was determined in these eggs by observing the development of the blastoderm, and calculated as the *number of eggs with a clearly developed blastoderm/total number of eggs $\times 100$* . All doubtful blastoderm development was recorded as "infertile" or "dead," depending on the apparent stage of development. Eighty eggs from the L&R-84-sperm females, and 84 from the Lake 7.1-sperm females were stored at 12°C for a maximum of 20 d, and then placed in an incubator at 38°C and 55% relative humidity (**RH**) for a further 20 days. They were then candled to determine the fertility rate, in this case calculated as the *number of fertile eggs at candling/total eggs $\times 100$* . Eggs with live embryos were maintained in a hatcher at 37.5°C and 70% RH for a further 5 days. Hatchability was defined as the ratio of the *number of offspring hatched over the total number of eggs deemed fertile by candling*.

Experimental Design

The influence of the type of extender on motility variables was assessed in semen samples collected from 19 adult red-legged partridge males once per wk from March to July. All samples were diluted 1:1 (v/v) at field temperature with either 1) L&R-84 medium (Lake and Ravie, 1984), composed of sodium-L-glutamate (1.92 g), glucose (0.8 g), magnesium acetate 4H₂O (0.08 g), potassium acetate (0.5 g), polyvinylpyrrolidone (**PVP**, relative molecular mass [Mr] = 10,000) (0.3 g), and H₂O (100 mL) (final pH 7.08, final osmolality 343 mOsm/kg), or 2) Lake 7.1 medium (Lake and Ravie, 1979), composed of sodium-L-glutamate (1.52 g), glucose (0.6 g), magnesium acetate 4H₂O (0.08 g), potassium citrate tribasic monohydrate (0.128 g), N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl)taurine (**BES**) (3.05 g), sodium hydroxide 1 N (to adjust the pH), and

Table 1. CASA-determined sperm motility variables (mean±SE) in semen samples diluted with L&R-84 and Lake 7.1.

Sperm motility variables	L&R-84	Lake 7.1	<i>P</i> -values
% Motile sperm	30.1 ± 1.2 ^b	46.0 ± 2.6 ^a	0.000
% Progressive motility	10.7 ± 0.7	13.6 ± 1.2	0.114
VCL (μm/s)	50.0 ± 1.4 ^a	43.0 ± 1.9 ^b	0.001
VSL (μm/s)	31.5 ± 1.3 ^a	26.3 ± 1.7 ^b	0.003
VAP (μm/s)	38.6 ± 1.3 ^a	32.6 ± 1.8 ^b	0.001
LIN (%)	59.1 ± 1.1 ^a	55.4 ± 1.8 ^b	0.017
STR (%)	78.1 ± 0.8 ^a	75.1 ± 1.5 ^b	0.039
WOB (%)	74.4 ± 0.7 ^a	71.1 ± 1.5 ^b	0.026
ALH (μm)	2.4 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.8	0.594
BCF (Hz)	8.1 ± 0.2	8.1 ± 0.3	0.326

^{a,b}Different letters within rows indicate significant differences between extenders.

H₂O (100 mL), (final pH = 7.10; final osmolality 370 mOsm/kg). They were then maintained at 5°C for 3 h before measuring sperm motility variables as described above.

The fertilization capacity of the sperm cells subjected to the different treatments was estimated from the results of 2 intravaginal AI procedures (see above), 3 apart from May to June, in 2 consecutive yr (2015/2016). Each yr, a total of 22 females (11 birds/treatment) was inseminated.

Statistical Analysis

Sperm variables are reported as mean ± SE; fertility data and penetration hole numbers as mean ± SEM. Sperm variables that were not normally distributed, as determined by the Shapiro–Wilk’s test, were arcsine-transformed or arcsinh-transformed (when the results included some zero values) before statistical analysis. Differences in sperm variables were assessed by repeated-measures ANOVA following the statistical model $x_{ijk} = m + A_i + a_{j(i)} + B_k + AB_{ik} + e_{ijk}$, where x_{ijk} = the measured sperm variable, m = the overall mean of variable x , A_i = the effect of extender ($i = 1-2$ treatments), $a_{j(i)}$ = the effect of a bird within a group, B_k = the effect of day of collection ($k = 1$ to 22), AB_{ik} = the interaction between A and B , and e_{ijk} = the residual (confounded with interaction between bird [$a_{j(i)}$] and day of collection [B_k]). The influence of the interaction *semen extender* \times *year* on fertilization capacity of chilled sperm was analyzed by two-way ANOVA, following the statistical model $x_{ijk} = m + A_i + B_j + AB_{ij} + e_{ijk}$, where x_{ijk} = the number of egg penetrations, m = the overall mean of variable x , A_i = the effect of extender ($i = 1-2$ treatments), B_j = the effect of year for artificial insemination ($j = 1$ to 2), AB_{ij} = the interaction between A and B , and e_{ijk} = the residual ($l = 1-164$). A post hoc Newman–Keuls test was performed to compare differences between the mean number of penetration holes at different times following AI. In addition, the association among fertility rate, embryonic mortality, and semen extender was assessed using the Chi-squared test. All statistical calculations were made

Table 2. Fertility rate, hatchability, and number of penetration holes (mean ± SEM) in eggs collected in the first 3 wk after AI.

	L&R-84	Lake 7.1	<i>P</i> -values
Penetration holes	17.7 ± 12.7 ^a	3.0 ± 1.0 ^b	0.033
Fertility (%) according to blastoderm development	18.8 ± 8.8 ^a	7.2 ± 2.8 ^b	0.049
Fertility (%) at 20 d incubation	29.8 ± 10.9 ^a	3.8 ± 3.8 ^b	0.001
Embryo mortality (%)	11.2 ± 3.6	1.6 ± 2.2	
Hatchability (%)	60.7 ± 10.7	50.0 ± 50.0	

^{a,b}Different letters within rows indicate significant differences between extenders.

using Statistica software v.13 (Dell Statistica, StatSoft Inc., Tulsa, OK).

RESULTS

Seminal Plasma Osmolality, Sperm Concentrations, and Sperm Volumes

The osmolality of the seminal plasma was 356.7 ± 4.8 mOsm/kg (range: 332 to 383 mOsm/kg). The mean sperm concentration and semen volume of the samples were $2034.1 \pm 87.8 \times 10^6$ sperm/mL and 15.7 ± 0.7 μL, respectively.

Quality of Red-legged Partridge Semen After Chilling for 3 h at 5°C with the Different Extenders

Motility The use of the L&R-84 extender was associated with better VCL ($P < 0.01$), VSL ($P < 0.01$), VAP ($P < 0.01$), LIN ($P < 0.05$), STR ($P < 0.05$), and WOB ($P < 0.05$) results. The use of the Lake 7.1 extender was associated with higher percentages of motile sperm ($P < 0.001$) (Table 1).

Penetration Holes A small number of penetration holes were found in non-fertilized eggs, but in much lower numbers than in fertilized eggs ($P < 0.001$). The mean number of penetrations was higher for the L&R-84-extended sperm ($P < 0.05$) (Table 2). With both extenders, the number of penetrations varied widely over the first 3 wk post AI; no holes were seen in the membranes of eggs collected in the fourth wk post AI. When the Lake 7.1 extender was used, the number of penetration holes was significantly higher in the second week after AI than at any other time ($P < 0.05$). When the L&R84 medium was used, no significant differences were seen between the numbers of penetration holes at any time (Table 3).

No clear correlation was seen between the change in the number of penetration holes (Table 3) and blastoderm development (Table 4).

Fertility The overall fertility rate, determined by both methods, was higher ($P < 0.05$) for birds inseminated with the L&R-84-extended sperm (Table 2). Embryonic mortality, however, tended ($P = 0.05$) to be

Table 3. Number of penetration holes (mean \pm SEM) in eggs collected during the first 4 wk after AI.

	1st Week	2nd Week	3rd Week	4th Week
Penetration holes with L&R-84	2.8 \pm 1.2 (range: 0–22)	6.6 \pm 3.4 (range: 0–83)	2.0 \pm 1.5 (range: 0–22)	0.0 \pm 0.0
Penetration holes with Lake 7.1	0.4 \pm 0.3 ^b (range: 0–6)	1.3 \pm 0.3 ^a (range: 0–4)	0.1 \pm 0.1 ^b (range: 0–1)	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b

^{a,b}Different letters within rows indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between weeks.

Table 4. Fertility (mean \pm SEM) according to blastoderm development in eggs collected during the first 4 wk after AI.

	1st Week	2nd Week	3rd Week	4th Week
Fertility (%) with L&R-84	30.3 \pm 3.0	18.8 \pm 6.2	10.0 \pm 5.0	0.0 \pm 0.0
Fertility (%) with Lake 7.1	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b	20.0 \pm 13.3 ^a	5.0 \pm 2.3 ^b	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^b

^{a,b}Different letters within rows indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between weeks.

higher in those inseminated with L&R-84. Hatchability was not affected by the extender used.

DISCUSSION

The present study shows that red-legged partridge semen extended with L&R-84 can be stored for at least 3 h at 5°C. The species' semen can therefore be transported if thus prepared and chilled, making the management of assisted reproduction easier.

The L&R-84 extender was the better of the 2 tested. The osmolalities of both extenders (343 mOsm/kg and 370 mOsm/kg for L&R-84 and Lake 7.1, respectively) were similar and within the range seen for seminal plasma (mean 357 mOsm/kg, range: 332 to 383 mOsm/kg); the differences in results cannot, therefore, be related to this variable. Both extenders also contained sodium glutamate and glucose, but differed in that L&R-84 contained PVP and had no BES zwitterion buffer, while Lake 7.1 had no PVP but did contain BES. PVP is an external cryoprotectant that helps protect against membrane injury during temperature changes. The reduction in temperature from 41°C (mean body temperature) to 5°C is likely stressful for the sperm cells; the protective presence of PVP might therefore explain the better results obtained with the L&R-84 extender. It should be remembered, however, that zwitterion buffers such as BES prevent the pH from varying much during chilling (Salamon and Visser, 1972), helping the stability of the plasma membrane to remain stable (Ijaz et al., 1989), and indeed, with rooster sperm, Lake 7.1 extender has previously returned better results than L&R-84 after 48 h of chilling (Villaverde-Morcillo et al., 2016). This suggests that the positive influence of this type of additive is ob-

served only after fairly long periods of storage. The tolerance to zwitterion buffers and the benefits they provide to sperm cells appear, however, to be species specific—at least in the mammalian species studied. Studies in rams, aoudad, and mouflon have highlighted the benefits of the zwitterion buffers TES, HEPES, and PIPES (Molinia et al., 1994; Santiago-Moreno et al. 2013; Pradiee et al., 2016), although TES seems to be harmful to ibex sperm (Santiago-Moreno et al. 2009). Differences in the response to the components of extenders and to short preservation times may be due to species-specific characteristics in sperm plasma membrane fluidity, its cholesterol/phospholipid ratio (Blesbois et al., 2005), and/or the osmotic tolerance of the cells (Blanco et al., 2000).

The reduced fertilization capacity of the sperm extended with Lake 7.1 may be the consequence of a direct influence on sperm cell functionality. The small number of holes per germinal disc recorded when the Lake 7.1 extender was used suggests that sperm cells thus treated fail in their attempt to traverse the utero-vaginal area and/or cannot complete the acrosome reaction. Acrosome integrity was not measured, but studies in chickens suggest that it is unlikely to be dramatically affected in diluted semen samples during short periods of storage (see Abouelezz et al., 2015b). Certainly, VCL, VSL, VAP, LIN, STR, and WOB were all negatively affected when Lake 7.1 was used. It is known that motile chicken sperm actively ascend the vagina and enter the sperm storage tubules (SST) (Allen and Grigg, 1958). Having arrived here, they progress through the oviduct by antiperistalsis to reach the infundibulum. Hence, the success of the sperm in fertilizing the egg is related to the motility characteristics that allowed it to reach the SST. SST emptying is also affected by sperm motility. Sperm from low-mobility ejaculates tends to exit the SST sooner than does fast-swimming sperm (Pizzari et al., 2008). Froman (2003) proposed that after sperm cells enter the SST, fluid secreted from the SST epithelial cells generates a current. Sperm able to reach a good velocity might be able to move against this current and remain within the tubule, emerging when their velocity declines to below a certain threshold. Froman's proposal suggests that a higher VSL and VAP might afford sperm cells an advantage in terms of fertilizing an egg.

Alternatively, the reduced fertilization capacity of the sperm extended with Lake 7.1 may be due to an adverse affect(s) on the genital tract. When glycerol is used in extenders for rooster sperm, changes in the osmolality of the female genital tract fluids can occur, along with alterations in the properties of its luminal fluid, and patterns of cilia motion (Hammerstedt and Graham, 1992; Chalah et al., 1999). However, Lake 7.1 has no additive with properties similar to those of glycerol, and thus alterations in these characteristics are unlikely. The reduced fertility related to the use of Lake 7.1 would therefore appear to be due to interference with sperm functionality (reduced motility).

In the egg penetration assay, no holes were recorded in the fourth wk post AI when either extender was used. This supports previous reports that red-legged partridge sperm remains viable for 3 wk in the female SST (Abouelezz et al., 2015a), as it does in chickens (Blesbois and Brillard 2007).

Fertility results are commonly affected by the frequency of AI. In chickens, inseminating twice (3 to 4 d apart) per wk is recommended to ensure the filling of the utero-vaginal glands, while in geese 3 inseminations per wk are recommended (Blesbois, 2012), and in guinea fowl, 2 consecutive d of insemination are needed in the first wk plus 2 per wk thereafter (Seigneurin et al., 2013). In the present work, just 2 inseminations per wk were used, and the fertility rates recorded were rather low; other frequencies of insemination should therefore be explored.

In conclusion, this paper describes, to the best of our knowledge, the first successful use of chilled red-legged partridge semen (stored for 3 h at 5°C). Extending with L&R-84 returned better sperm velocity values than extending with Lake 7.1. Further studies are needed to determine whether the semen of this species can be stored chilled for longer periods.

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